

Scientific colonialism: a new form of exploiting

Sina was happy with his new position as a PhD student. Nevertheless, after a while, he realized that his supervisor did not have the required expertise for his research. So, he found a co-supervisor with more relative expertise.

Although he designed his research qualitatively and stressed that he is not a quantitative analyst, the co-supervisor changed the method to quantitative. So, he redesigned his research and collected data. The main problem was raised when Sina needed guides for data analysis. He did not know which method, software, and statistics should be applied for data analysis and how he should interpret the results.

In parallel with self-study, he asked his co-supervisor for help, but his emails were remanded unresponsive for several months. He asked his supervisor for a solution. She responded, "I am not familiar with the topic and method of your study, and you should not expect the co-supervisor to help you because he has 20 PhD students and various administrative tasks. The entire responsibility of doing your research is yourself, and you should search for solutions or find people who can help you." When Sina said, "I have found you and the co-supervisor for help beforehand," she became nervous and denied her responsibilities.

After several discussions, Sina realized that his supervisors expected to act as reviewers instead of supervisors and coauthors. He understood why every one of his supervisors has more than 400 papers, books, or other publications in their resume. Why do they have around 20 PhD students, various classes, and conferences, and simultaneously, they are the director of an institute or faculty dean?

It is impossible for a supervisor that do all these duties correctly and possess this amount of publication unless they abuse their PhD student as scientific laborers. This unethical treatment is a new form of exploitation that can called "Scientific colonialism."

The questions arise here are:

1. If some supervisors set up a scientific colony by participating in innovative ideas and efforts of their PhD students without accomplishing their responsibilities as a supervisor and a coauthor?
2. Has the ethical challenge of scientific colonialism been considered in the framework of research integrity?
3. If no restriction exists on the number of PhD students for a supervisor?
4. Is there an efficient mechanism for monitoring and stopping the scientific colonialism of some supervisors in academia?